

Beyond Recall@K: Six Metrics for Evaluating Multilingual Image-Text Retrieval in Vision-Language Models

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Abstract. In today’s times, application of vision-language models (VLMs) for multilingual image-text retrieval has become ubiquitous. When we are dealing with cross-lingual or multilingual settings, traditional evaluation metrics like Recall@K don’t capture all the performance nuances of VLMs. To the best of the author’s knowledge, in a multilingual application setting, existing benchmarks don’t provide sufficient insights into retrieval consistency, semantic agreement or stability across languages. When a given text is translated into multiple languages, the retrieval results can vary a lot, and this variation in results is not fully captured by the traditional evaluation frameworks. In this paper, 6 metrics have been introduced that will help in analyzing various facets of multilingual retrieval capabilities of VLMs: Cross-Language Retrieval Agreement (CLRA), Cross-Language Retrieval Drop (CLRDR), Cross-Language Retrieval Robustness (CLRR), Multilingual Retrieval Stability Index (MRSI), Language Ranked Retrieval Spread (LRRS), and Semantic Embedding Retrieval Agreement (SERA). FAISS-based retrieval outputs from translated queries were used to compute the metrics. In this study, the metrics were evaluated upon 4 VLMs: CLIP, AltCLIP, SigLIP and SigLIP-2. The Flickr30k dataset was used in the studies. The languages used in this paper are English (anchor language), French, Spanish, German, Italian, Dutch and Hindi. MarianMT was used for translating the english captions to the other languages used in the paper. On these 6 metrics it was observed that SigLIP-2 consistently performed better than CLIP, AltCLIP and SigLIP. AltCLIP performed moderately well and better than CLIP, while CLIP had the most retrieval variance across languages. SigLIP’s performance was better than CLIP and AltCLIP and less than SigLIP-2 in most scenarios. Applications where multilingual retrieval assessment is quintessential, these 6 metrics can be used to get a more holistic evaluation. These 6 metrics will complement the standard metrics that exist and will be primarily beneficial in evaluating a VLM’s performance in low resource or multilingual applications.

Keywords: multilingual image-text retrieval · vision-language models · cross-language evaluation metrics · retrieval consistency · low-resource language benchmarking · CLIP, AltCLIP, SigLIP and SigLIP-2

1 Introduction

Vision-language Models (VLMs) such as CLIP [5], AltCLIP [1], SigLIP [9], SigLIP-2 [7] have facilitated us with a broad range of cross-modal capabilities, including image-text retrieval. With the spread of globalization, performance of models in a multilingual setting becomes quite critical in various real-world applications (e.g., search engines, multilingual media archives). In a multilingual environment of an application, a single input text query might be translated into multiple languages of interest, and the expectation will be that the retrieval results should be consistent, traditional metrics like Recall@K fail to capture the retrieval consistency aspect of the application. There are chances that VLMs might showcase high variance in retrieval performance across multiple languages, especially in low resource languages. Recall@K is a standard evaluation metric in evaluating image-text retrieval applications, where the emphasis is on evaluating image-centric ranking and the inter-language variation is not the focus. For example, Recall@K does not assess whether the retrieval results of the VLMs are semantically aligned across various languages. To the best of the author’s knowledge, there isn’t a holistic benchmark currently that helps in evaluating the true multilingual capabilities of a retrieval model. Despite the presence of several multilingual datasets (e.g., Multi30k [2], CrossModal3600 [6]), often the performance of the models on an individual language is evaluated in isolation. There isn’t a holistic evaluation framework that takes into account a model’s consistency, robustness, semantic alignment, and dispersion across multiple languages. This makes it challenging to compare models’ performance in a multilingual setting or make changes to improve the cross-lingual generalization capabilities of a model. This paper proposes a multi-faceted evaluation framework to assess the multilingual image-text retrieval capabilities of a model. This framework has 6 novel evaluation metrics: 1. Cross-Language Retrieval Agreement (CLRA) 2. Cross-Language Retrieval Drop (CLRD) 3. Cross-Language Retrieval Robustness (CLRR) 4. Language Ranked Retrieval Spread (LRRS) 5. Multilingual Retrieval Stability Index (MRSI) 6. Semantic Embedding Retrieval Agreement (SERA) These metrics will help in deriving complementary insights to the existing standard evaluation metrics; it will be primarily invaluable in assessing the model’s performance across both high-resource and low-resource languages.

2 Related Work

CLIP [5] was a seminal paper that showcased a dual encoder model trained on image and english text pairs, which aided in zero shot performance in vision-language tasks. AltCLIP [1] further extended upon CLIP by replacing the english-only text encoder with a multilingual one (XLM-R), in order to improve the retrieval performance in non-english languages. The SigLIP [9] paper introduced the sigmoid-based contrastive loss approach which replaced the softmax formulation used in CLIP, which in turn led to robust training and better alignment

across diverse data. SigLIP-2 [7] is one of the latest state-of-the-art VLMs that is built on the strong foundations of the SigLIP framework with the integration of self-distillation and masked prediction losses for robust training achieving better performances in a multilingual setting. Multi30k [2] and CrossModal3600 [6] are some of the prominent datasets used to evaluate multilingual image-text retrieval capabilities of models. These benchmarks typically report recall@k per language, treating it as a retrieval task for each individual language. Most studies don't evaluate the performance of retrieval across multiple languages at the same time-whether the same input query yields semantically consistent results across translated languages. Though Recall@k is a standard metric, it does not evaluate cross-language variance, semantic alignment or robustness in multilingual retrieval systems. This paper tries to fill the gap in evaluating multilingual VLM systems by capturing various facets such as consistency (CLRA, CLRD), robustness (CLRR), semantic alignment (SERA), and rank variability (LRRS, MRSI).

3 Proposed Metrics

3.1 Cross-Language Retrieval Agreement (CLRA)

Purpose In a multilingual setting, if an input query is translated to multiple languages of interest, the expectation is that the VLM in use should retrieve the same or similar images for the translated languages as well. CLRA will aid in measuring the retrieval agreement for the translated languages.

Definition For an input query (image caption), top-k images will be retrieved, and for each language pair, Jaccard similarity is calculated for the retrieved images. After that the average Jaccard is calculated for all the language pairs for an input query and post that it is averaged across all the input queries (image captions) in the dataset. Mathematically, CLRA is computed as follows:

$$\text{CLRA}_k = \frac{1}{|I|} \sum_{i \in I} \left(\frac{1}{|P_i|} \sum_{(l_1, l_2) \in P_i} \frac{|R_{i, l_1}^{(k)} \cap R_{i, l_2}^{(k)}|}{|R_{i, l_1}^{(k)} \cup R_{i, l_2}^{(k)}|} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where:

- I = set of all image IDs
- P_i = set of all language pairs for image i
- $R_{i, l}^{(k)}$ = top- k retrieved images using language l as the query for image i

Interpretation A high CLRA score means that there is a high semantic alignment in the retrieval results across the languages of interest. The intersection of union numbers will be higher when the retrieval outputs are consistent and stable over various translations. CLRA score will be 1 when for a given k value all the image caption queries return the same set of images across all language pairs.

What it Captures CLRA aims to capture the degree of semantic agreement across languages, which indirectly will help in understanding a model’s generalization capabilities for translations of the same query. This will be invaluable in evaluating the robustness of cross-lingual search systems or multilingual content platforms.

Limitations The CLRA metric does not take into account the ranking order of the top-k results, it focuses on the set overlap. It is also sensitive to the value of k, lower numbers of k might amplify the differences more when compared to high values of k.

3.2 Cross-Language Retrieval Drop (CLRD)

Purpose In multilingual environments, retrieval performance of low-resource languages might not be optimum. CLRD helps us in quantifying how much retrieval performance drops when we’re switching from a high-resource language (generally English) to target languages.

Definition For a given input query (image caption), retrieval is first performed on the anchor language (English in this study) and the rank of the ground-truth image is noted down. After that the retrieval is done for the translated languages and the rank of the ground-truth image for each language is computed. For a given target language, a drop is the difference of the rank of the ground truth image in the target language and the anchor language (English). For a given target language, these rank differences are calculated for all the input queries and summarized by mean, median, p95, etc.

$$\text{CLRD}_L = \frac{1}{|I| \cdot |L|} \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{l \in L} \left(\text{rank}_i^{(l)} - \text{rank}_i^{(\text{en})} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where:

- $\text{rank}_i^{(l)}$ = rank of the correct image using language l as the query
- $\text{rank}_i^{(\text{en})}$ = rank using the English query
- I = set of all image IDs
- L = set of all non-English languages

Interpretation A low CLRD value indicates that there is consistency in the retrieval results across multiple languages. A high CLRD value indicates that there are limitations in a model’s multilingual capabilities, particularly low-resource languages.

What it Captures This metric enables us to analyze the performance degradation per language. This helps us in understanding which languages’ results are not optimal when we are switching from the anchor language and retrieval stability across translations. This metric will be invaluable in studying retrievals in low resource or morphologically rich languages.

Limitations The metric can be sensitive to outliers that’s why percentile statistics (median, p25, etc) have been included.

3.3 Cross-Language Retrieval Robustness (CLRR)

Purpose The objective of this metric is to check if a multilingual VLM succeeds in retrieving the correct image for at least one of the translated languages for a given query and k value.

Definition For a given input query (image query), the top-k images are fetched for each translated language. If the ground-truth image exists in at least one translated language result, then CLRR@K is considered a success. If none of the translated languages is able to fetch the ground truth image in its retrieved results for given k, it is considered a failure. CLRR score is primarily computing the proportion of input queries for which at least one non-english or translated language succeeded.

$$\text{CLRR}_k = \frac{1}{|I|} \sum_{i \in I} \mathbf{1} \left[\exists l \neq \text{en} : \text{rank}_i^{(l)} \leq k \right] \quad (3)$$

Where:

- $\mathbf{1}[\cdot]$ is the indicator function (1 if true, 0 otherwise)
- I is the set of all image IDs
- l iterates over all non-English languages
- $\text{rank}_i^{(l)}$ is the retrieval rank of image i when queried in language l

Interpretation A high CLRR score denotes high multilingual robustness, even if the anchor language’s retrieval results are excluded, at least one translated language is capable of fetching the right image for a given k.

What it Captures The metric primarily checks if atleast one translated language is able to fetch the correct results for a given k and an input query.

Limitations This metric is purely binary in nature, it checks if one of the translated languages fetched the right image for a given k, it doesn’t reward scenarios where multiple languages might have retrieved the correct image for a given k.

3.4 Language Ranked Retrieval Spread (LRRS)

Purpose The objective of this metric is to quantify the spread of the retrieval rank of the ground truth image across languages for an input query.

Definition For an input query (image caption), the retrieval rank of the ground truth image for each language is first extracted. LRRS is the difference between the maximum and minimum retrieval ranks of the ground truth image across languages. LRRS is calculated for all the input queries and summarized by mean, median, p95, etc.

$$\text{LRRS}_i = \max_l \left(\text{rank}_i^{(l)} \right) - \min_l \left(\text{rank}_i^{(l)} \right) \quad (4)$$

Then, the average LRRS across all image queries is:

$$\text{LRRS} = \frac{1}{|I|} \sum_{i \in I} \text{LRRS}_i \quad (5)$$

Where:

- I = set of all image queries in the dataset
- l = language used for the text query
- $\text{rank}_i^{(l)}$ = rank position of the ground-truth image for image query i when the query is in language l
- LRRS_i = retrieval rank spread for query i across languages (max minus min)
- LRRS = average spread across all image queries

Interpretation A low LRRS score indicates there is consistency in the retrieved results across languages, the ranks are most likely in the similar range. A high LRRS indicates that retrieval consistency is not optimal and there is instability in the multilingual application.

What it Captures In multilingual systems, where translated queries are involved, this metric captures the intra-query variability in retrieval ranks.

Limitations Since, LRRS score is based on max-min rank difference, it can be sensitive to outliers especially when the multilingual system involves a low resource language. Keeping that in mind, LRRS has been calculated twice, one iteration by including Hindi and in another iteration excluding Hindi.

3.5 Multilingual Retrieval Stability Index (MRSI)

Purpose This metric is primarily to understand the stability of the retrieved results across languages and get an insight on the fluctuation of the rank of the ground truth image across various translated queries in the system.

Definition For a given input query (image caption), MRSI calculates the standard deviation of the ranks of the ground truth images across various languages. This is calculated for all the input queries and summarized by mean, median, p95, etc.

$$\text{MRSI}_i = \text{std} \left(\left\{ \text{rank}_i^{(l)} \right\}_{l \in L_i} \right) \quad (6)$$

Then, the overall score is:

$$\text{MRSI} = \frac{1}{|I|} \sum_{i \in I} \text{MRSI}_i \quad (7)$$

Where:

- I : Set of all image IDs (queries) in the dataset
- L_i : Set of all languages used for image i
- $\text{rank}_i^{(l)}$: Retrieval rank of the correct image i when using language l as input
- MRSI_i : Standard deviation of ranks for image i across all languages
- MRSI : Final score averaged over all image queries

Interpretation A low MRSI score indicates that all the languages have similar ranks of the ground truth image. A high MRSI score indicates that there is a lot of variance in the ranks of the ground truth image across images, indicating instability of the model in a multilingual setting.

What it Captures In a statistically robust manner, MRSI captures the spread of the retrieval quality across languages.

Limitations The standard deviation approach can still be sensitive to outliers in systems that have low resource languages. In this study, Hindi is a low resource language. Keeping that in mind, MRSI has been calculated twice, one iteration by including Hindi and in another iteration excluding Hindi. Another limitation of the metric is if there is an instability based on the high metric numbers, it doesn't exactly tell which language or languages in the system is causing the instability.

3.6 Semantic Embedding Retrieval Agreement (SERA)

Purpose The goal of this metric is to quantify the semantic similarity in the retrieval results across multiple languages even when the image IDs might be different. This is invaluable in assessing multilingual systems where the retrieval IDs might be different but could be semantically aligned.

Definition For a given input query (image caption), the top-k images are fetched for each language in the system. For each language, the mean of the embeddings of the top-k retrieved images is calculated. After this, the cosine similarity between the mean embeddings of various language pairs in the system is calculated. For a given query, the average of the cosine similarities of the language pairs is calculated. This is done for all the queries in the system, and the average SERA@K for the dataset is calculated.

$$\text{SERA}_k = \frac{1}{|I|} \sum_{i \in I} \left(\frac{1}{|P_i|} \sum_{(l_1, l_2) \in P_i} \cos(\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{i, l_1}^{(k)}, \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{i, l_2}^{(k)}) \right) \quad (8)$$

Where:

- $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{i, l}^{(k)}$: mean embedding of the top- k retrieved images for image i , using language l as query
- P_i : set of all language pairs for image i
- $\cos(\cdot, \cdot)$: cosine similarity function
- I : set of all image queries

Interpretation A high SERA score indicates that even if the retrieved image IDs across languages are quite different they are semantically closer in the embedding space. This indirectly indicates that there is strong semantic alignment in the results across various language queries. A low SERA score indicates that there is inconsistency in the semantic alignment in the retrieval results.

What it Captures SERA score tries to capture the retrieval agreement in the semantic space instead of just image IDs, this complements the CLRA metric. This metric can be very useful in systems that have multiple diverse images representing the same concept.

Limitations The SERA metric depends on the quality of the image embeddings. If the embeddings used don't represent the semantic closeness, then the SERA score might misrepresent agreement. It might not be sensitive to semantic drift when image embeddings of unrelated content are close in the vector space.

4 Evaluation Setup

4.1 Dataset and Captions

The Flickr30k dataset [8] was used for the benchmark studies in this paper. The dataset contains 31K images and 5 captions per image. For each image, the first 2 captions were chosen for the studies.

4.2 Language Coverage

All the english captions were translated to the following languages using MarianMT [4]: French (fr), German (de), Spanish (es), Italian (it), Dutch (nl), and Hindi (hi). A low resource language like Hindi was chosen to test the robustness of the VLM.

4.3 Vision-Language Models (VLMs)

This study involved 4 pre-trained VLMs: CLIP, AltCLIP, SigLIP and SigLIP-2. In the original papers, CLIP was trained on English-only data, AltCLIP introduced a multilingual text encoder, SigLIP introduced a sigmoid-based contrastive loss in place of softmax, SigLIP-2 further built on the strong foundations laid by the SigLIP framework. All the models were used in zero-shot mode without any fine tuning on the Flickr30k dataset. All the models used in this study were loaded from Hugging Face with the following specific variants:

- CLIP: `openai/clip-vit-base-patch32`
- AltCLIP: `BAAI/AltCLIP`
- SigLIP: `google/siglip-so400m-patch14-384`
- SigLIP-2: `google/siglip2-so400m-patch14-384`

Different variants of the models might yield different retrieval results.

4.4 Embedding Generation

The model’s visual encoder was used to generate the image embeddings. The model’s language encoder was used to generate the text embeddings for the captions (for all the languages). For each image, the first 2 captions were taken and the mean embedding of 2 captions per language were calculated.

4.5 Retrieval Method

FAISS [3] was used for approximate nearest neighbor search for efficiency. For each input query (per language), the top-k images were retrieved based on cosine similarity computations in the embedding space.

4.6 Metric Computation

All the metrics were computed using the top-k retrieval outputs. All the metrics were calculated at the image level, then they were aggregated across the entire dataset. For certain metrics (LRRS, MRSI), special attention was given to Hindi which is a low resource language, the metrics were computed once by including Hindi and then in the next iteration by excluding Hindi.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Summary of Results

The performance of the 4 VLMs: CLIP, AltCLIP, SigLIP and SigLIP-2 were evaluated across 6 proposed metrics (CLRA, CLRD, CLRR, LRRS, MRSI, SERA) in this study. Metrics such as MRSI and LRRS were calculated with and without Hindi to showcase the impact of low-resource languages. SigLIP-2 performed best across all the 6 metrics.

5.2 Metric-Wise Analysis

Cross-Language Retrieval Agreement (CLRA) SigLIP-2 showcased high agreement amongst language pairs, especially at top-1, top-3 and top-5, indicating better stability in the retrieval results. SigLIP’s performance was also competitive enough performing better than CLIP and AltCLIP at various top-k levels, however, it was less performant than SigLIP-2. CLIP consistently had low scores across various k values showcasing low retrieval consistency across languages. AltCLIP performed better than CLIP but was below the metric numbers from the SigLIP family of models.

Table 1. CLRA@k scores across models

Top-K	CLIP	AltCLIP	SigLIP	SigLIP-2
1	0.0404	0.0902	0.2440	0.3367
3	0.0383	0.0696	0.1626	0.2219
5	0.0418	0.0716	0.1559	0.2115
10	0.0487	0.0792	0.1590	0.2134
20	0.0579	0.0916	0.1693	0.2249
50	0.0736	0.1136	0.1895	0.2484
100	0.0888	0.1343	0.2081	0.2695

Cross-Language Retrieval Drop (CLRD) SigLIP-2 had the lowest drop when transitioning from English to non-English languages showcasing less performance degradation in multilingual scenarios. CLIP had the highest drops showcasing limitations in multilingual generalization. AltCLIP performed better than SigLIP in mean and p95, suggesting lesser extreme retrieval failures, whereas SigLIP performed better than AltCLIP in terms of median and percentage of cases with minimal drop ($\% < 100$), indicating better overall consistency despite occasional extreme outliers.

Table 2. CLRD Aggregate scores across models

Agg	CLIP	AltCLIP	SigLIP	SigLIP-2
Mean	4409.6119	1542.3723	2399.1766	569.8461
Median	665	55	4	1
p95	22951.8500	10151	19615	3043.7000
$\% < 100$	28.5059	56.6234	73.4663	80.6689

Cross-Language Retrieval Recall (CLRR) SigLIP-2 showcased the highest robustness scores with 99% queries returning the correct image in at least one non-English language in the top-100, outperforming the other models especially

at the top-1, top-5 and top-10 levels. SigLIP’s performance was second best with 97% in the top-100, but a substantial gap in performance was observed at top-1, top-5 and top-10 levels when compared with SigLIP-2. AltCLIP’s performance was moderately well with 89% in the top-100 while CLIP’s robustness was at 62% in the top-100.

Table 3. CLRR@k scores across models

Top-K	CLIP	AltCLIP	SigLIP	SigLIP-2
1	0.0942	0.3083	0.5998	0.7679
5	0.2161	0.5277	0.7931	0.9059
10	0.2897	0.6227	0.8560	0.9429
25	0.4105	0.7485	0.9197	0.9741
50	0.5105	0.8303	0.9527	0.9870
100	0.6181	0.8941	0.9744	0.9944

Language-Ranked Retrieval Spread (LRRS) When Hindi was included in the study of this metric, SigLIP-2 had a smaller spread in ground-truth ranks across languages. SigLIP-2 outperformed all the other models at various aggregation levels. AltCLIP performed better than SigLIP and CLIP, when Hindi was included. CLIP showcased the highest spread. When the metric was calculated by excluding Hindi, it was observed that SigLIP performed the best followed by AltCLIP and SigLIP-2. CLIP showcased high spread even with the exclusion of Hindi. AltCLIP was second best in both the scenarios, with and without Hindi.

Table 4. LRRS Aggregate scores across models - Include Hindi

Agg	CLIP	AltCLIP	SigLIP	SigLIP-2
Mean	16163.1716	7376.5345	13829.0888	3008.1655
Median	16211	4606	13062.5	802
p25	8868	1483	5774	129
p75	23429.75	11308.75	21421.75	3442.5
p95	29407.35	23469.4999	28936.0499	14425.0999
%<100	0.0129	2.1281	0.4385	22.2319

Table 5. LRRS Aggregate scores across models - Exclude Hindi

Agg	CLIP	AltCLIP	SigLIP	SigLIP-2
Mean	5286.0736	1215.3457	401.8339	2515.6765
Median	2315.5	218	26	444
p25	522	43	3	49
p75	7675.75	998	163	2558
p95	20488.35	6115.6999	1936.6999	13205.0999
%<100	9.1636	36.7866	68.9656	32.1597

Multilingual Retrieval Stability Index (MRSI) When Hindi was included in the study of the metric, SigLIP-2 showcased the lowest standard deviation highlighting consistent multilingual behavior. AltCLIP’s performance was better than SigLIP and CLIP, across all the aggregation levels when Hindi was included. CLIP’s performance was least effective amongst all the models. When Hindi was excluded from the metric computation, SigLIP performed the best followed by AltCLIP and SigLIP-2. CLIP’s numbers were higher and its performance was least effective even when Hindi was excluded. AltCLIP was second best in performance in both the scenarios: with and without Hindi.

Table 6. MRSI Aggregate scores across models - Include Hindi

Agg	CLIP	AltCLIP	SigLIP	SigLIP-2
Mean	5577.7035	2556.2324	4824.4677	1058.6938
Median	5595.8418	1594.5822	4555.4571	283.8376
p25	3083.0777	514.6049	2014.0930	45.7067
p75	8037.0361	3921.3923	7479.3166	1212.5005
p95	10081.6639	8130.9091	10089.4403	5084.4099
%<100	0.1064	6.3133	1.3252	34.4103

Table 7. MRSI Aggregate scores across models - Exclude Hindi

Agg	CLIP	AltCLIP	SigLIP	SigLIP-2
Mean	1910.7491	438.4541	146.7237	935.1597
Median	837.6602	78.6872	9.3169	163.9783
p25	186.8985	15.3460	1.2134	17.8885
p75	2771.2629	359.0255	59.1333	949.4172
p95	7330.4009	2203.7196	703.0302	4910.6848
%<100	17.5437	54.1691	80.8925	43.5707

Semantic Embedding Retrieval Agreement (SERA) All the models had high SERA scores in the top-10, but SigLIP-2 had higher numbers when compared to CLIP, AltCLIP and SigLIP in top-1 score. Even though the retrieved image IDs might have been different, there was semantic alignment, which will be helpful in downstream semantic tasks.

Table 8. SERA@k scores across models

Top-K	CLIP	AltCLIP	SigLIP	SigLIP-2
1	0.5673	0.6213	0.6679	0.7649
5	0.7913	0.8271	0.8298	0.8875
10	0.8365	0.8703	0.8662	0.9163

5.3 Model-Wise Comparison

Since CLIP was primarily trained on English data, it performed inefficiently in most of the multilingual metrics in this study. CLIP’s retrieval was more oriented towards the English semantics, and it didn’t generalize well in non-english input queries. AltCLIP, which replaces CLIP’s language encoder with XLM-R, performed better than CLIP in most of the metrics, but still struggled with low resource languages like Hindi. SigLIP, performed better than CLIP and AltCLIP in most of the metrics, its sigmoid-based contrastive loss approach could be one of the reasons for its retrieval robustness. The SigLIP-2 model which was built on the strong foundations of the SigLIP framework and further enhanced performed better than CLIP, AltCLIP and SigLIP on most of the metrics. SigLIP-2’s multilingual robustness makes it a good choice in today’s time to use in a multilingual retrieval system.

5.4 Effect of Low-Resource Language

Hindi was chosen for this study as it is a low resource language and it will help in understanding the retrieval capabilities of VLMs in a multilingual system where one of the languages is low resource. All the models showed high instability when Hindi was used in the metrics: LRRS, MRSI. SigLIP-2, even though it was impacted, still showed better stability even with Hindi, showcasing its better handling of low resource languages. This emphasizes that certain metrics should be studied with and without low resource languages to fully understand a model’s robustness.

6 Conclusion

Traditional metrics like recall@k are insufficient to evaluate the performance of VLMs comprehensively in a multilingual system. There’s a dearth of benchmark

systems that assesses retrieval consistency, semantic alignment and robustness of models in a multilingual system. This paper introduced 6 metrics: CLRA, CLRD, CLRR, LRRS, MRSI and SERA that will help in evaluating performance of a model in a multilingual setting. These metrics individually cover various facets of a model in a multilingual setting: overlap, robustness, semantic similarity, variance, and stability. The metrics were evaluated on the Flickr30k dataset and on 7 languages (English + 6 translated languages via MarianMT). Four VLMs were evaluated in this study: CLIP, AltCLIP, SigLIP and SigLIP-2. The primary observation was that SigLIP-2 outperformed the other models in the majority of metrics. AltCLIP was moderately better than CLIP. CLIP was primarily trained on English-only data, which led to inferior performance in a multilingual context. Hindi as a low resource language introduced instability in the model performance, certain metrics (LRRS, MRSI) were calculated by including and excluding Hindi to showcase the instability a low resource language can bring to a multilingual system. The objective of this work has been to develop a model-agnostic framework to evaluate multilingual retrieval capabilities of models. This framework will be invaluable in assessing systems where VLMs are integral like global search engines, cross-cultural media platforms and multilingual content systems. Future work involves expanding to more languages. The current work was related to image retrieval, this can be extended to video or document retrieval.

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